

Copper(II) nitrobenzoate complexes with 4-ethylmorpholine and 2,6-dimethylmorpholine

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Abstract : New copper(II) nitrobenzoate complexes with the saturated diheterocyclic bases (L-L) : 4-ethylmorpholine and 2,6-dimethylmorpholine, have been prepared and characterized by physico-chemical and spectroscopic methods. They are magnetically dilute and antiferromagnetic, with stoichiometries of the type $\text{Cu}(\text{OCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2\text{-x})_2 (\text{B})_n$ ($x = 4, 3$ and 2 ; $\text{B} = \text{L-L} = 4\text{-ethylmorpholine}$ for $n = 1$ and $2,6\text{-dimethylmorpholine}$ for $n = 0.5, 1$ or 2). The spin-exchange parameter, $-2J$, for some antiferromagnetic complexes has been evaluated from both magnetic susceptibility and EPR measurements at different temperatures.

Keyword : Copper(II) complexes, antiferromagnetic complexes, heterocyclic base.

Copper(II) carboxylates form both magnetically dilute and antiferromagnetic complexes with nitrogen and oxygen donor ligands¹⁻⁶. The structure of the complexes depends upon factors such as the steric and electronic characteristics of the ligand, stoichiometry of the complex, and reaction conditions⁶⁻⁹. Oxygen donor organic ligands and pyridine type nitrogen donors generally give antiferromagnetic complexes with copper(II) carboxylates^{3-5,8,9}, whereas saturated amine donors prefer to form magnetically dilute complexes^{1,2,9,10}. The influence of the steric and electronic characteristics of pyridine-type ligands on the structural and magnetic properties of their complexes have been the subject of systematic investigations⁷⁻⁹, but no reports exist on saturated diheterocyclic bases. In the present study, the complexation properties of substituted morpholines, viz. 4-ethylmorpholine (4-EtMorph) and 2,6-dimethylmorpholine (2,6-Me₂Morph) (having both nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms present simultaneously in the same ligand) with copper(II) nitrobenzoates have been undertaken. An additional incentive to undertake these studies was to see if the boat form of the diheterocyclic base could be stabilized in the complexed state.

Experimental

Liquid heterocyclic bases such as 4-EtMorph and 2,6-Me₂Morph (K and K laboratories) were dried by refluxing and distilling over sodium hydroxide pellets before use. The purity of 2-, 3- and 4-nitrobenzoic acids (B.D.H., L.R.) was checked from their sharp melting points after recrystallization from ethanol. Copper(II) sulphate (B.D.H.) was used as

such. Acetone, n-hexane and solvent ether, all from B.D.H., were purified by usual methods.

Preparation of copper(II) nitrobenzoates (o-, m- and p-) : A solution of nitrobenzoic acid (5 g, 30 mmol) in a minimum quantity of acetone (30 ml) was neutralized with aqueous sodium hydroxide (1.19 g; 30 mmol) solution (7 ml). A small quantity (10 mg) of the nitrobenzoic acid was added to make the solution just acidic and the solution was then filtered. Filtered solution of copper(II) sulphate (3.735 g; 15 mmol) in distilled water was then added to the stirred solution of sodium nitrobenzoate. The precipitate gets separated out after the contents had been stirred for 0.5 h. It was then filtered, washed with distilled water and dried in air. The air-dried product was then subjected to vacuum at 140 °C for 3 h.

Preparation of the complexes : A solution of the stoichiometric amount or of 50% excess, of the saturated heterocyclic base dissolved in acetone or ether (15 cm³) (Table 1) was added dropwise to a continuously stirred suspension of copper(II) nitrobenzoate (1 g) in the same solvent (30 cm³). Solid adducts of some bases separated after the contents had been stirred for two hours. Other complexes were separated on concentrating the reaction mixture to about 1/5th of its original volume, cooling in the refrigerator for 4 h and adding n-hexane (n.h.) in excess. The separated product was filtered through a G₄ filtration unit, washed with n-hexane and dried under vacuum.

Table 1. Elemental analysis data (%), colour and particulars of the method of preparation of the complexes

Compd. (Composition) [Formula weight]	Elemental analysis (%) :				Colour	S.a. ^a / excess	Ether(e) ^b / acetone (a)	Just stirring ^c / cooling or cooling + n.h.
	Found (Calcd.)							
	Cu	C	H	N				
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (4-EtMorph) (C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₉ Cu) [510.5]	12.38 (12.46)	47.12 (47.13)	4.11 (3.92)	8.70 (8.24)	Greenish yellow	Excess	e	-
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5} (C ₁₇ H _{14.5} N _{2.5} O _{8.5} Cu) [453]	13.99 (13.97)	45.42 (45.08)	3.30 (3.09)	7.92 (7.72)	Light bluish green	S.a.	e	-
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) (C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₉ Cu) [510.5]	12.25 (12.46)	47.33 (47.13)	4.04 (3.92)	8.70 (8.24)	Sky blue	S.a.	a	Cooling + n.h.
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂ (C ₂₆ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ Cu) [625.5]	10.16 (10.18)	50.51 (50.06)	5.63 (5.13)	8.94 (8.97)	Violet	Excess	a	Cooling + n.h.
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (4-EtMorph) (C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₉ Cu) [510.5]	12.32 (12.46)	47.58 (47.13)	4.01 (3.92)	8.62 (8.24)	Bluish green	Excess	e	-
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5} (C ₁₇ H _{14.5} N _{2.5} O _{8.5} Cu) [453]	13.68 (13.97)	45.42 (45.08)	3.52 (3.09)	7.99 (7.72)	Greenish blue	S.a.	e	-
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) (C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₉ Cu) [510.5]	12.37 (12.46)	46.99 (47.13)	4.19 (3.92)	7.99 (8.24)	Bluish green	S.a.	e	-
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂ (C ₂₆ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ Cu) [625.5]	10.20 (10.18)	49.89 (50.06)	4.93 (5.13)	8.77 (8.97)	Light blue	Excess	e	-
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (4-EtMorph) (C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₉ Cu) [510.5]	12.14 (12.46)	46.90 (47.13)	3.55 (3.92)	7.99 (8.24)	Bluish green	Excess	e	-
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5} (C ₁₇ H _{14.5} N _{2.5} O _{8.5} Cu) [453]	13.74 (13.97)	45.12 (45.08)	3.21 (3.09)	7.04 (7.72)	Bluish green	S.a.	e	-
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) (C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₉ Cu) [510.5]	12.32 (12.46)	47.63 (47.13)	3.81 (3.92)	7.98 (8.24)	Pale blue	S.a.	e	-
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂ (C ₂₆ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ Cu) [625.5]	10.38 (10.18)	50.55 (50.06)	5.56 (5.13)	9.01 (8.97)	Bluish green	Excess	e	-

^aIndicates whether the heterocyclic base was taken in stoichiometric amount (S.a.) or in excess.

^bIndicates whether the solvent taken was acetone (a) or ether (e).

^cIndicates whether the complex separated on just stirring/cooling or addition of n-hexane (n.h.) was also needed.

Carbon and hydrogen analyses were performed on an automatic Coleman-33 analyser, while nitrogen was analysed by Kjeldahl's method in the departmental microanalytical laboratory. The copper content was estimated volumetrically by EDTA titration using xylenol orange as indicator.

IR spectra of copper(II) nitrobenzoate (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) complexes with heterocyclic bases and anhydrous sodium benzoates were recorded both as nujol and hexachlorobutadiene (HCBD) mulls on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer with sodium chloride plates as windows in 4000–600 cm⁻¹ region and far-IR (600–250 cm⁻¹) spectra were recorded as Nujol mulls in polythene films. Electronic reflectance spectra of the complexes (either neat or diluted with

MgCO₃) were recorded on a Unicam SP-700 UV-visible spectrophotometer equipped with a SP-735 diffuse reflectance attachment (range : 50000–4000 cm⁻¹). The X-band EPR measurements (9.439–9.442 GHz) of powdered materials at room temperature were made on a JES-FE3XG electron paramagnetic resonance spectrometer while the X-band EPR measurements (8.916–9.19 GHz) of powdered materials of three complexes at different temperatures were made on a Varian E-4 electron paramagnetic resonance spectrometer. Diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) was used as calibrant.

Room-temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements of all the complexes were made on finally powdered samples using a Gouy balance and Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant.

Table 2. Some coordinatively diagnostic features of IR spectra (cm⁻¹) of sodium salts of carboxylate groups and their copper(II) complexes

Compd	$\nu_a(\text{OCO})$	$\nu_s(\text{OCO})$	$\nu(\text{Cu-O})$	$\nu(\text{Cu-N})$	Suggested mode of binding
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (4-EtMorph)	1610	1410	415	300	Bridging bidentate
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5}	1600	1394	414	304	Bridging bidentate
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂	1590	1384	424	290	Chelating bidentate
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂	1592	1359	399	294	Chelating bidentate
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (4-EtMorph)	1645	1400	390	300	Bridging bidentate
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5}	1645	1390	408	300	Bridging bidentate
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂	1610	1380	400	296	Bridging bidentate
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂	1600	1355	480	300	Chelating bidentate
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (4-EtMorph)	1658	1395	434	294	Bridging bidentate
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5}	1610	1410	400	315	Bridging bidentate
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂	1608	1380	370	295	Bridging bidentate
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂	1600	1370	455	345	Chelating bidentate
4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COONa	1597	1395	-	-	-
3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COONa	1612	1385	-	-	-
2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COONa	1605	1390	-	-	-

Table 3. Electronic reflectance spectral data (cm⁻¹) and room temperature μ_{eff} values of the magnetically dilute and antiferromagnetic adducts of the copper(II) nitrobenzoates with substituted morpholines

Compd	Absorption I <i>d-d</i> transitions	Absorption II Ligand → metal charge-transfer transitions	μ_{eff}
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph)	15150	-	1.82
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂	19230	31750	2.10
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂	16390	33330	2.10
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂	14490	29850	1.77
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (4-EtMorph)	12660	33330	1.64
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -4) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5}	14285	-	1.61
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (4-EtMorph)	12660	38460	1.57
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5}	13880	-	1.60
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -3) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂	13330	35710	1.70
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (4-EtMorph)	14800	37040	1.58
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5}	13790	30770	1.55
Cu(OOCC ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -2) ₂ (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) ₂	14080	34480	1.69

ant The magnetic susceptibilities of two of the complexes at different temperatures were measured on a Vibrating Sample Magnetometer PAR-155 with variable temperature cryostat. The measured susceptibility was corrected for the diamagnetic susceptibility of the ligands. The correction for temperature independent paramagnetism was taken as 60 × 10⁻⁶ cgs units per gram atom of copper(II) ions.

Results and discussion

Chemical formulae and colours for the complexes are given in Table 1. Examination of Table 1 shows that all copper(II) nitrobenzoates give rise to complexes of 1 : 1 (metal-base) stoichiometry with the saturated heterocyclic base, 4-ethylmorpholine while the base 2,6-dimethylmorpholine yields complexes of 1 : 0.5, 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 (metal-base) stoichiometries with copper(II) nitrobenzoates. The synthesis of the adducts of copper(II) nitrobenzoates with substituted morpholines follows the following reactions.

where $x = 2, 3$ or 4 ; $n = 1$ for $\text{L-L} = 4\text{-EtMorph}$ and $n = 0, 0.5, 1$ and 2 for $\text{L-L} = 2,6\text{-Me}_2\text{Morph}$.

The complexes are insoluble in organic solvents and do not melt but decompose above 250 °C. The interest in the present investigations was to see the role of pK_a of the parent carboxylic acid on the structure and the effect of steric and electronic properties of the six-membered saturated diheterocyclic amine having basicity of a high order ($pK_a > 7.5$) on the stoichiometry, magnetic behaviour and structure of the complexes.

Table 4. Electron paramagnetic resonance spectral parameters, values of spin exchange parameter, $-2J$ (cm^{-1}), of antiferromagnetic copper(II) complexes and $\text{p}K_a$ of axial ligand and carboxylic acid

Compd.	g_{\perp}	g_{\parallel}	g_{av}	$ D $ (cm^{-1})	Carboxylic acid $\text{p}K_a$	Axial ligand $\text{p}K_a$	$-2J$
$\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-4)_2(4\text{-EtMorph})$	2.0926	2.3384	2.1745	0.3494	3.367	7.670	272 ± 5 (EPR)
$\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-4)_2(2,6\text{-Me}_2\text{Morph})_{0.5}$	2.0995	2.5142	2.2377	0.3874			
$\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-3)_2(4\text{-EtMorph})$	2.0441	2.3669	2.1517	0.3930	3.462	7.670	288 ± 1 (EPR)
$\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-3)_2(2,6\text{-Me}_2\text{Morph})_{0.5}$	2.1031	2.5861	2.2641	0.4075			
$\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-3)_2(2,6\text{-Me}_2\text{Morph})$	2.0923	2.5403	2.2416	0.4068	3.462	8.600	256 (Mag. sus.)
$\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-2)_2(4\text{-EtMorph})$	2.0349	2.4127	2.1608	0.3830	2.183	7.670	266 ± 13 (EPR)
$\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-2)_2(2,6\text{-Me}_2\text{Morph})_{0.5}$	2.1328	2.4534	2.2397	0.3952			
$\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-2)_2(2,6\text{-Me}_2\text{Morph})$	2.1087	2.4641	2.2772	0.3869	2.183	8.600	226 (Mag. sus.)

IR spectral studies : Since both the acetate group and the diheterocyclic base can coordinate to the metal ion in a bidentate or monodentate fashion, many structural arrangements are possible in principle. In the absence of definitive structural data, two criteria are currently employed to determine the coordinating mode of acetate group, viz. (i) the ' Δ criterion'^{7,12} is based upon the difference in the $\nu_a(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{OCO})$ values, and (ii) the 'directions of shifts criterion'¹³ which depends upon the directions of the $\nu_a(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{OCO})$ shifts in the complexes, compared to their values in sodium nitrobenzoates. Of these, the latter criterion is considered to be more important. The important infrared absorption frequencies and suggested mode of binding of carboxylate group of complexes under discussion are listed in Table 2. Both bridging bidentate and chelating bidentate mode of coordination of the carboxylate group is present in the complexes. A shift to the lower energy region ($\approx 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the bands due to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ vibrations in the complexes of the base 2,6-Me₂Morph relative to those in the free base (≈ 3300) indicates the coordination of the base through nitrogen atom of the N-H bond¹⁴. However, in the complexes of the base, 4-EtMorph, containing N-C₂H₅ group too the absorption due to $\nu(\text{C-H})$ of the >N-C₂H₅ disappears. This indicates that nitrogen atom of >N-C₂H₅ group in the complexes coordinates to the metal ion. A band observed around 1100 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{OCO})$ vibration in free morpholine ligand undergoes a negative shift of $5\text{--}25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes which suggests coordination of these bases through oxygen atom also. Additional bands compared with the far IR spectra of uncomplexed copper(II) nitrobenzoates and free bases in the regions $370\text{--}480$ and $290\text{--}345 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have tentatively been assigned to $\nu(\text{Cu-O})$ and $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ modes, respectively¹⁵.

An examination of the infrared spectra of all the complexes under study reveals a close similarity to those of the free bases and no new bands of low or medium intensity (characteristic of boat configuration) appear in the region

$1500\text{--}700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, thus indicating the bases to be coordinated in the same form as in the free state, i.e. in the chair form^{16,17}.

Electronic reflectance spectral studies : All magnetically dilute copper(II) complexes (Table 3) under discussion show a broad band in the region $15150\text{--}19230 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be assigned to the ${}^2T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2E_g$ ligand field transition for an octahedral field. The broadness or splitting observed for this main band is ascribed to tetragonal distortion. The lower and higher energy components of this can be assigned, respectively to the ${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ (or $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) and ${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ ($d_{xz}, d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) ligand-field transitions for a tetragonal field¹⁸⁻²⁰. In the present case the complexes are bound to be distorted due to the large difference in the ligand field strengths of carboxylate ligands and the bases. Another band around $31750\text{--}33330 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been assigned to the ligand \rightarrow metal charge transfer transition.

Two absorptions (Table 3), one as a broad band in the region $12660\text{--}16390 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (band I) and the other as a shoulder around $29850\text{--}38460 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (band II), are observed for antiferromagnetic copper(II) complexes under study. Band I may be due to the absorption corresponding to the $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xz}, d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ electronic transitions for copper(II) ion in tetragonal environments²¹. The band II can be assigned to the $2p\pi(\text{O}) \rightarrow (d_{x^2-y^2})^*$ charge-transfer transition; the appearance of this band is considered to be characteristic of the dimeric structure for the copper(II) carboxylate complexes²¹⁻²³.

Electron spin resonance studies : The X-band EPR curves of powdered materials for two of the magnetically dilute copper(II) complexes, viz. $\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-x)_2(\text{L})_2$ ($x = 3$ and 2 and $\text{L} = 2,6\text{-Me}_2\text{Morph}$) obtained at room temperature are consistent with axial symmetry of the complexes except for $[\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-4)_2(2,6\text{-Me}_2\text{Morph})]$

Fig. 1. Electron paramagnetic resonance spectrum of [Cu(OOCC₆H₄NO_{2-x})₂(2,6-Me₂Morph)_{0.5}] at room temperature.

which has EPR spectrum (Fig. 1) typical of elongated rhombic geometry [g_z (2.21) > g_y (2.07) > g_x (2.03)]. The magnitudes of $g_{||}$ (2.28–2.30) and g_{\perp} (2.04–2.05) obtained from the EPR spectrum for these complexes are consistent with an elongated tetragonal type structure which agrees with the results obtained from electronic absorption studies^{19,20}. The observed range of $g_{||}$ is in conformity with the CuO₄N₂ chromophore of the complex²⁴.

The X-band EPR spectra at 300 K for powdered samples of antiferromagnetic complexes under present discussion (Table 4) contain absorption lines at field strengths of 600 (H_{\parallel}), 4700 (H_{\perp}) and 6100 G (H_{22}), which are characteristic features of axially symmetric binuclear copper(II) species and correspond to the spin triplet state ($S = 1$) with $D > h\nu$ and $E = 0$ ^{25,26}. The range of $g_{||}$ or g_z (2.33–2.58), g_{\perp} (2.03–2.13) and D (0.34–0.40 cm⁻¹) evaluated from the EPR spectra are comparable with the earlier reported values for binuclear copper(II) carboxylate complexes⁴⁻⁷. However, in addition to the above-mentioned absorptions, an absorption line around 3200 G is also observed. The intensity of this line increases while the intensity of the lines due to triplet state, as expected decreases with the lowering of temperature. This line is, therefore, attributed to the magnetically dilute copper(II) arylcarboxylate complexes^{25,27,28}.

Magnetic susceptibility studies : Room-temperature magnetic moment values for the copper(II) complexes lie in the ranges 1.77–2.10 and 1.55–1.70. In view of the μ_{eff} value for the former complexes lying above the spin-only value and for the latter being close to the value reported for dinuclear or polynuclear complexes, where carboxylate group acts as a bridge between two metal ions, the copper(II) complexes have been categorised as (i) magnetically dilute and (ii) antiferromagnetic complexes¹⁻⁷ respectively.

Two of the antiferromagnetic complexes, viz. Cu(OOCC₆H₄NO_{2-x})₂(2,6-Me₂Morph) ($x = 3$ and 2), have also been characterized by magnetic susceptibility measurements at different temperatures. The magnetic moment value for these two complexes decrease with temperature, thus confirming their antiferromagnetic behaviour. The fol-

lowing modified equation based upon Bleaney and Bowers' model²⁹ was employed to evaluate the exchange parameter ($-2J$) from magnetic susceptibility data at different temperatures^{27,28}.

$$\ln \left[\frac{N\bar{g}^{-2}\beta^2(1-x)}{kT\left(\chi_{Cu} - \frac{0.43x}{T} - N_{\alpha}\right)} - 3 \right] = -2J/kT$$

or $\ln(F - 3) = -2J/kT$

The unknown quantities in the above expression on the L.H.S. were as follows : the value of \bar{g} was determined from EPR measurements and the value of N_{α} was taken to be 60×10^{-6} cgs units. The value of x , the mole fraction of the paramagnetic impurity was so chosen as to fit in well with the above expression. The value of $2J$ has been determined from the slope [$2J/k$] of the straight line obtained from a plot of $\ln(F - 3)$ vs $1/T$. The values of $2J$ for three of the complexes, viz. Cu(OOCC₆H₄NO_{2-x})₂(4-EtMorph) ($x = 4, 3$ and 2) (Table 4) was also calculated from the variation of intensity (I) of the EPR lines at the temperatures 223 K, 173 K and 113 K using the relation^{25,28}.

$$\frac{A_1}{A_2} = \frac{I_1}{I_2} = \frac{T_2(3 + e^{-2J/kT_1})}{T_1(3 + e^{-2J/kT_2})}$$

The relative areas of curves [A_1/A_2] at two different temperatures (T_1 and T_2) were estimated by the reported methods^{30,31}. The values of $-2J$ determined by the two methods are comparable and lie between 226–288 cm⁻¹.

In spite of the high basicities of these bases ($pK_a = 8-9.6$), this range of values of $2J$ is comparable to that for the earlier reported copper(II) carboxylate complexes with terminal ligands of low basicity, e.g. py etc. No consistent trend of the variation of $-2J$ with pK_a of the acids or the ligand is obtained.

In the present investigation, complexes of 1 : 0.5 (metal : base) stoichiometry are found to be antiferromagnetic, complexes of 1 : 2 stoichiometry are found to be magnetically dilute and that of 1 : 1 stoichiometry are found to be both antiferromagnetic as well as magnetically dilute. On the basis of all the studies we can conclude the following : In the magnetically dilute complexes, viz. Cu(OOCC₆H₄NO_{2-x})₂(2,6-Me₂Morph)₂ ($x = 4, 3$ and 2), since no major ab-

Fig. 2

sorption has been observed in the region 9000–11000 cm^{-1} , *trans*-configuration [Fig. 2 (a or b)] with CuO_4N_2 chromophore, where carboxylate group acts as a chelating bidentate ligand, is proposed^{19,32} In these complexes, the base coordinates through the oxygen atom. Moreover, since the Jahn-Teller distortion in the copper(II) complexes is considered to be tetragonal elongation and the heterocyclic bases are stronger ligands than the carboxylate anions, *trans*-in-plane structure [Fig. 2(b)] seems to be the obvious choice for $\text{CuO}_4(\text{O}_2)$ chromophore in the present complexes. For the complexes of 1 : 0.5 stoichiometry, i.e. of type $\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-x)_2(\text{L-L})_{0.5}$ (Table 3), $\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2)_2(\text{dioxane})_{0.5}$ like polymeric structure³³ with *syn-syn* bridging carboxylate groups forming dinuclear units connected by L-L bases is suggested. For the antiferromagnetic complexes of 1 : 1 stoichiometry, i.e. of the type $\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-x)_2\text{B}$ (Table 3), binuclear copper(II) acetate monohydrate like structure where carboxylate group acts as a *syn-syn* bridging bidentate ligand is assigned. Monomeric square pyramidal or polymeric distorted octahedral structure where the 4-nitrocarboxylate group acts as a chelating bidentate is assigned for the $\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2-4)_2(2,6\text{-Me}_2\text{Morph})$ complex [Fig. 2(c)].

Amongst morpholines, 4-ethylmorpholine forms antiferromagnetic complexes with all the copper(II) nitrobenzoates. While 2,6-dimethylmorpholine yields both magnetically dilute as well as antiferromagnetic complexes with copper(II) nitrobenzoates. These results show that steric hindrance of the amine ligands plays an important role in determining the stoichiometry, structure and hence the magnetic properties of the complexes. No complex of the saturated diheterocyclic bases (L-L) could be isolated which contains any of the bases in the boat conformation, i.e. the diheterocyclic bases are present in their chair form. It is explicable in terms of comparatively larger stability of chair conformation than the boat form due to less steric congestion or repulsions in the former than in the latter. No consistent correlation of $-2J$ values with $\text{p}K_a$'s of acids or of the terminal ligands is obtained. This result is disappointing but in view of the earlier reports it is not surprising.

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